

Taxonomic Revision of Genus *Gonatista* Saussure, 1869 (Mantodea: Epaphroditidae: Gonatistinae)

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Abstract. Taxonomic revision of the genus *Gonatista* Saussure, 1869. One new species is described, *quisqueyana* n. sp. from Hispaniola. *Gonatista borinquensis* nom. nov. is proposed for the misapplied *Mantis reticulata* Thunberg, 1815. *Gonatista bifasciata* (de Haan, 1842) is reinstated with *cubensis* Saussure, 1869 as a junior synonym. *Mantis grisea* Fabricius, 1793 is rendered **nomen dubium**, and *Mantis reticulata* Thunberg, 1815 is transferred to *Tarachodes* Burmeister, 1838.

The genus *Gonatista* was originally erected by Saussure in 1869 to accommodate *cubensis*, a Cuban species that he personally collected. The genus was then limited in scope by Saussure himself in 1871 when he merged several species names into a poorly defined and ultimately arbitrary concept of *Mantis grisea* Fabricius, 1793. In doing so, Saussure not only synonymized his own *cubensis* under *grisea* but also included *Mantis bifasciata* de Haan, 1842—a distinct Cuban species described decades earlier—and *Mantis reticulata* Thunberg, 1815, another species of ambiguous identity and dubious provenance. The result was a cluster of nominal taxa collapsed under *grisea*, a name with little diagnostic utility.

Caudell's 1912 revision of *Gonatista*, though limited, was the first to openly question the synonymy introduced by Saussure in 1871. He expressed doubt that the names then synonymized under *grisea* referred to a single species, noting morphological distinctions among at least four forms from North America and the Caribbean. Recognizing the absence of type data and the broad vagueness of early diagnoses, Caudell maintained *grisea* for the common species of the Southern United States and Cuba, used *phryganoides* Audinet-Serville, 1839 for the small maculate species from Hispaniola, and arbitrarily applied the name *reticulata* to a third Caribbean species, erroneously transferring *bifasciata* and *cubensis* to its synonymy. He also described a fourth and largest species from Hispaniola under a new name, *major*. Importantly, Caudell acknowledged the provisional nature of his taxonomy, conceding that, “a future study of the types of the old authors may show the above nomenclature to be faulty but for the present no better arrangement seems possible.” This candid admission highlights both the limitations of the resources available to him and his awareness of the need for future revisionary work based on primary type material.

The genus then fell into taxonomic neglect for another century until Lombardo & Perez-Gelabert offered their brief revision of *Gonatista* in 2004. These authors undertook a more extensive revision of the genus, using freshly collected material from across Hispaniola. Their study revalidated *reticulata* for the island and described *jaiba* as a new species based on male genital morphology. Continuing the modern

revisionary trajectory of the genus, Anderson then provided another reassessment of *Gonatista* taxonomy in 2021, clarifying historical synonyms and refining morphological boundaries among the known species. Drawing from original descriptions, historical type localities, and comparative morphometrics, Anderson placed *bifasciata* and *cubensis* as junior synonyms of *grisea*, reversing Caudell's unsupported 1912 reassignment of both names to *reticulata*. He highlighted that Caudell had neither examined female specimens nor justified his synonymy, despite the fact that both *bifasciata* and *cubensis* are morphologically consistent with *grisea* and occur outside the known distribution range of *reticulata*. In addition to correcting these taxonomic placements, Anderson provided the first dichotomous keys for Caribbean *Gonatista* females, differentiating taxa based on body proportions, forewing maculation, and abdominal morphology. This work confirmed the validity of five species within the genus—*grisea*, *phryganoides*, *reticulata*, *major*, and *jaiba*.

Following the publication of his 2021 Caribbean text, Anderson (2024) conducted a detailed examination of the Mantodea material originally described by Carl Peter Thunberg, housed at Uppsala University. This investigation revealed that *Mantis reticulata* Thunberg, 1815—the name historically applied to a key Caribbean species of *Gonatista*—was in fact misassigned. The *reticulata* holotype was determined to represent an African species of *Tarachodes* Burmeister, 1838. Consequently, *reticulata* was deemed a misapplied name and its longstanding position within the genus was challenged. This finding prompted a broader reevaluation of *Gonatista* taxonomy, leading the present author to reassess the foundation of the genus itself. Upon further scrutiny, *grisea*—the oldest name still anchoring the genus—was found to be equally problematic. The description of *grisea*, combined with its associated locality and morphological traits, aligned more convincingly with the Asian genus *Humbertiella* Saussure, 1869 than with any member of *Gonatista*. With the two senior-most names (*reticulata* and *grisea*) now excluded from *Gonatista*, a formal revision of the genus became necessary to rectify its taxonomy, stabilize nomenclature, and clarify species boundaries based on defensible morphological and biogeographic criteria.

The present revision seeks to resolve these longstanding taxonomic issues by reevaluating all known names historically associated with *Gonatista*, incorporating examination of type specimens where possible, and integrating new morphological and biogeographic data. In doing so, this work redefines species boundaries within the genus and restores nomenclatural clarity to one of the most historically entangled groups of Neotropical Mantodea.

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Gonatista Saussure, 1869

Description. Habitus of moderate stature, broad, flattened, stocky. Male more slender, more robust in female. Base color generally consists of mottled grays, browns, and greens. Head capsule wide, embossed. Vertex slightly elevated above dorsal surface of compound eyes, juxtaocular tubercles salient, bluntly conical in shape. Ocelli large in male, much less so in female. Lower frons very narrow, approximately five times wider than tall, superior margin arched. Compound eyes rounded, bulging. Antennae filamentous. Pronotum flattened, widened anteriorly, margins unarmed to finely denticulate, surface with broad, blunted tubercles, providing lumpy appearance. Metazona narrows toward base, widening toward supracoxal dilation, where margins remain parallel throughout prozona. Prosternum with coxal furrows along margins. Forecoxae longer than metazona. Forefemora with dorsal margin arched at base, sinuate beyond, armed with 4 posteroventral, 4 discoidal, 10-14 anteroventral spines. Discoidal spines straight, posteroventral spines somewhat curved inward, anteroventral spines alternating in length between short and long. Tibial spur groove positioned near base. Foretibiae with 4-7 posteroventral spines, basal and distal spines longer than middle four spines; 9-12 anteroventral spines, each slightly increasing in length before terminating in spur. Metathoracic femora lacking genicular spine. Basitarsi of

metathoracic tibiae as long as or slightly longer than other tarsomeres combined. Male forewings surpassing abdomen, broad with wide costal area, subhyaline, irregularly reticulated, somewhat wrinkled. Female forewings significantly shorter than abdomen, opaque, costal area wide. Male hindwings hyaline, interspersed with gray on veins; female hindwings smoky. Abdomen flattened, both sexes with lobed lateral margins, more prominent in female. Supra-anal plate large, triangular.

Type Species: *Gonatista cubensis* Saussure, 1869

Species Checklist:

- *Gonatista bifasciata* (de Haan, 1842) **stat. res.**
- *Gonatista borinquensis* **nom. nov.**
- *Gonatista jaiba* Lombardo & Perez-Gelabert, 2004
- *Gonatista major* Caudell, 1912
- *Gonatista phryganoides* (Audinet-Serville, 1839)
- *Gonatista quisqueyana* **n. sp.**

Key to *Gonatista* Males:

- 1 Foretibiae glabrous. Prosternum pigmented yellowish with contrasting black maculation 2
- 1' Foretibiae densely ciliated. Prosternum pigmented light orange with reddish-brown maculation ...
..... *G. phryganoides*
- 2 Medium habitus. Body length measuring 36–47 mm in length; forewings measuring 30–41 mm. Pronotum robust, pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona <3.6. Coxal lobes unicolorous with anterior surface pigmentation of forecoxae 3
- 2' Large habitus. Body length measuring 52–63 mm in length; forewings measuring 41–49 mm. Pronotum narrow, pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona >3.7. Coxal lobes blackened *G. major*
- 3 Pronotum elongated and narrow; pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation >2.5, pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona >3.3. Anterior surface of forecoxae with small, whitish nodules interspersed throughout or with whitish nodules absent. Occurs in Hispaniola, Puerto Rico and Virgin Islands 4
- 3' Pronotum short and robust; pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation <2.3, pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona <3.3. Anterior surface of forecoxae with whitish nodule row lined just beneath anteroventral margin. Occurs in The Bahamas, Cuba, Jamaica, and the southeastern United States *G. bifasciata*
- 4 Pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation ≥ 2.6 , pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona ≥ 3.5 . Anterior surface of forecoxae colored orange. Occurs throughout mesic and montane zones of Hispaniola, Puerto Rico or Virgin Islands 5
- 4' Pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation <2.6, pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona <3.3. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored reddish-brown. Precinctive to Jaragua Peninsula xeric zone of Hispaniola *G. jaiba*
- 5 Metazona length to prozona length ≥ 1.2 . Lateral cervical sclerites pigmented black in basal half, anterior half colored dirty yellow. Foreleg trochanters pigmented reddish throughout. Occurs in Puerto Rico and Virgin Islands *G. borinquensis*
- 5' Metazona length to prozona length <1.2. Lateral cervical sclerites pigmented black, thinly margined on anterior with dirty yellow. Foreleg trochanters pigmented orange, occasionally margined in black around coxal lobes and base of forefemora. Occurs in Hispaniola
..... *G. quisqueyana*

Key to *Gonatista* Females:

- 1 Pronotum elongated and narrow; pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation >2.4, pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona >3.1. Occurs in Hispaniola, Puerto Rico and Virgin Islands 2
- 1' Pronotum short and robust; pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation <2.1, pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona <2.8. Occurs in The Bahamas, Cuba, Jamaica, and the southeastern United States *G. bifasciata*
- 2 Medium habitus. Body length measuring 40–47 mm in length; pronotum length 11-13.5; forewings measuring 21–25 mm. Coxal lobes unicolorous 3
- 2' Large habitus. Body length measuring 49–53 mm in length; pronotum length 14-16.5; forewings measuring 26–32 mm. Coxal lobes blackened *G. major*
- 3 Metazona length to prozona length ≥ 1.3 . Anterior surface of forecoxae colored reddish-purple with salient whitish nodules interspersed throughout. Lateral cervical sclerites pigmented black in basal half, anterior half colored dirty yellow. Occurs in Puerto Rico and Virgin Islands
..... *G. borinquensis*
- 3' Metazona length to prozona length ≤ 1.2 . Anterior surface of forecoxae colored reddish-brown, smooth. Lateral cervical sclerites pigmented black, thinly margined on anterior with dirty yellow. Occurs in Hispaniola *G. quisqueyana*

Note: females of *G. jaiba* and *G. phryganoides* are unknown.

Gonatista bifasciata (de Haan, 1842) **stat. res.**

Diagnosis. Male and female. Prosternum pigmented dirty yellow with large, black maculation between forecoxae. Lateral cervical sclerites pigmented black in basal half, anterior half colored dirty yellow. Forecoxae with 4-5 widely spaced teeth along anteroventral margin. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored reddish-brown in both sexes with whitish nodule row lined just beneath anteroventral margin, coxal lobes and trochanters unicolorous. Foretibiae glabrous. Meso/metathoracic legs glabrous. Male pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation 2.3; pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona 3.3; metazona length to prozona length 1.2; pronotum width at supracoxal dilation to pronotum width at base of metazona 1.4. Female pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation 2.1; pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona 2.8; metazona length to prozona length 1.1; pronotum width at supracoxal dilation to pronotum width at base of metazona 1.3.

Holotype: ♀ Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden

Type Locality. Cuba

Distribution. The Bahamas, Cuba, Jamaica and United States of America

Measurements. (all measurements are in millimeters and rounded to nearest 0.5) *Male.* Body length 36-43; pronotum length 8-11; forewing length 30-37; prothoracic coxa length 7-9; prothoracic femur length 9-11; metathoracic femur length 9-12. *Female.* Body length 36-45; pronotum length 9-12; forewing length 18-23; prothoracic coxa length 8-9; prothoracic femur length 11-13; metathoracic femur length 10.5-11.

Gonatista borinquensis **nom. nov.**

Diagnosis. Male and female. Prosternum pigmented light yellow with large, black maculation between forecoxae. Lateral cervical sclerites pigmented black, thinly margined on anterior with dirty yellow. Forecoxae with 3-4 widely spaced teeth along anteroventral margin. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored reddish in male, surface smooth, coxal lobes and trochanters unicolorous. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored reddish-purple in female with small, whitish nodules interspersed throughout, coxal lobes unicolorous. Foretibiae glabrous. Meso/metathoracic legs glabrous. Male pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation 2.7; pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona 3.5;

metazona length to prozona length 1.2; pronotum width at supracoxal dilation to pronotum width at base of metazona 1.3. Female pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation 2.5; pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona 3.5; metazona length to prozona length 1.3; pronotum width at supracoxal dilation to pronotum width at base of metazona 1.4.

Holotype: ♂ Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History, Washington D.C.

Type Locality. Mayagüez, Puerto Rico

Distribution. Puerto Rico and Virgin Islands

Measurements. *Male.* Body length 40-47; pronotum length 11-12; forewing length 36-40; prothoracic coxa length 7.5-8; prothoracic femur length 9-11.5; metathoracic femur length 10.5-12. *Female.* Body length 40-47; pronotum length 11-13.5; forewing length 21-25; prothoracic coxa length 7.5-8.5; prothoracic femur length 12-14; metathoracic femur length 11.5-12.

Gonatista jaiba Lombardo & Perez-Gelabert, 2004

Diagnosis. Male prosternum pigmented dirty yellow with large, black maculation between forecoxae. Lateral cervical sclerites pigmented black, thinly margined on anterior with dirty yellow. Forecoxae with 4-5 widely spaced teeth along anteroventral margin. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored reddish-brown with small, whitish nodules interspersed throughout, coxal lobes and trochanters unicolorous. Foretibiae glabrous. Meso/metathoracic legs glabrous. Male pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation 2.5; pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona 3.3; metazona length to prozona length 1.2; pronotum width at supracoxal dilation to pronotum width at base of metazona 1.3. Female unknown.

Holotype: ♂ Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia.

Type Locality. Oviedo, Pedernales, Dominican Republic

Distribution. Hispaniola

Measurements. *Male.* Body length 40; pronotum length 11.5; forewing length 41.

Gonatista major Caudell, 1912

Diagnosis. Male and female. Prosternum pigmented dirty yellow with large, black maculation between forecoxae. Lateral cervical sclerites pigmented black in basal half, anterior half colored dirty yellow. Forecoxae with 4-5 widely spaced teeth along anteroventral margin. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored orange in both sexes, surface smooth, coxal lobes blackened, trochanters unicolorous. Foretibiae glabrous. Meso/metathoracic legs glabrous. Male pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation 2.6; pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona 3.7; metazona length to prozona length 1.2; pronotum width at supracoxal dilation to pronotum width at base of metazona 1.4. Female pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation 2.5; pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona 3.1; metazona length to prozona length 1.2; pronotum width at supracoxal dilation to pronotum width at base of metazona 1.3.

Holotype: ♂ Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History, Washington D.C.

Type Locality. Santo Domingo, Santo Domingo, Dominican Republic

Distribution. Hispaniola

Measurements. *Male.* Body length 52-63; pronotum length 12.5-14.5; forewing length 41-49; prothoracic coxa length 8.5-9.5; prothoracic femur length 12.5-14; metathoracic femur length 13.5-14. *Female.* Body length 49-53; pronotum length 14-16.5; forewing length 26-32; prothoracic coxa length 11; prothoracic femur length 15-17; metathoracic femur length 14.

Gonatista phryganoides (Audinet-Serville, 1839)

Diagnosis. Male. Prosternum pigmented light orange with reddish-brown maculation between forecoxae. Lateral cervical sclerites pigmented reddish-brown, thinly margined on anterior with orange. Forecoxae with 5-7 well spaced denticles along anteroventral margin. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored orange, surface smooth, coxal lobes and trochanters unicolorous. Foretibiae densely ciliated. Meso/metathoracic legs significantly ciliate throughout. Male pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation 2.7;

pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona 3.5; metazona length to prozona length 1.1; pronotum width at supracoxal dilation to pronotum width at base of metazona 1.3. Female unknown.

Holotype: ♂ Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris

Type Locality. "Northern America"

Distribution. Hispaniola

Measurements. *Male.* Body length 34.5-36; pronotum length 7.5-9.5; forewing length 26-32; prothoracic coxa length 7.5; prothoracic femur length 8-10.5; metathoracic femur length 8.

Gonatista quisqueyana **n. sp.**

Type Material. ♂ Holotype: Arroyo Frio, La Vega, Dominican Republic 01.01.2020 MArmenteros leg. Anderson Collection Las Vegas. ♀ Allotype: Arroyo Frio, La Vega, Dominican Republic, 12.21.19 MArmenteros leg. Anderson Collection Las Vegas. 3 ♂ Paratypes: Arroyo Frio, 18°59'34"N 70°35'12"W, La Vega, Dominican Republic 11.20-12.21 MArmenteros leg. Anderson Collection Las Vegas. 1 ♀ Paratype: Arroyo Frio, 18°59'34"N 70°35'12"W, La Vega, Dominican Republic 10.20.21 MArmenteros leg. Anderson Collection Las Vegas.

Description. Habitus broad, flattened. Body color largely gray, variably mottled with darker greens, browns, and black, thereby strongly resembling bark or lichen. Males predominantly gray with moderate degree of black mottling, uncommonly whitish-gray with blackish mottling. Females have much higher color variation with heavier black and greenish mottling.

Head capsule. Vertex slightly elevated above dorsal surface of compound eyes, juxtaocular tubercles salient. Ocelli configured in tight grouping between bases of antennae, more salient in male. Antennae filiform, reaching metazona in female, significantly longer in male, reaching two-thirds length of abdomen. Compound eyes large, prominent, kidney-shaped, pigmented light gray. Lower frons approximately five times wider than tall, sinuous in middle, traversed with black band that extends into pigmentation of compound eyes on either side.

Pronotum flattened, widened anteriorly, margins finely denticulate. Supracoxal sulcus marked between two elevations on anterior end of metazona and two broadened tubercles on posterior end of prozona, giving pronotum a lumpy appearance. Margins of supracoxal dilation remain parallel toward anterior margin of prozona. Coloration of pronotum largely gray, variably mottled with darker greens, browns, and black. Prosternum pigmented light yellow with large, black maculation between forecoxae. Mesosternum light yellow, longitudinally striped with 3 reddish-brown bands that begin at base of prosternum.

Prothoracic legs. Forecoxae with 3-4 widely spaced teeth along anteroventral margin, posteroventral margin denticulate. Coxal lobes divergent; external lobe larger. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored orange in male, reddish-brown in female, smooth, coxal lobes unicolorous. Forefemora dilated, being widest toward base, forming confluent seam with lateral pronotal margins when in repose. Forefemora with 4 black-tipped posteroventral spines, 4 discoidal, and 10-12 black anteroventral spines. Dorsal margin of forefemora sinuous, serrated with row of small, whitish teeth; additional row of larger, ivory-colored, blunted nodules runs down median of posterior surface, numbering 6-7 in male and 7-8 in female, with those of female being larger and rounder. Anterior surface of forefemora colored orange in male, reddish-brown in female. Foretibiae with 6-7 reddish-brown, black-tipped posteroventral spines, first and last spine longer than middle four, and 12 reddish-brown, black-tipped anteroventral spines. Tibial spur dark reddish-brown to black. Anterior surface of foretibiae colored orange in male, reddish-brown in female.

Meso/metathoracic legs annulated with darker mottling. Basitarsi longer than remaining segments combined.

Wings. Male forewings well exceed length of abdomen, broad, gray-hyaline, marked with light green to gray along primary veins, variably interspersed with larger, linear blotches and smaller, more rounded, brownish or blackish maculations. Costal area of forewings expanded laterally, reticulate, largely hyaline. Discoidal area pigmented with extensive light gray to green casting bordering costal ridge and extending into middle of discoidal area. Stigma white, linear, often faded or concealed among mottling.

Female forewings extend one-half length of abdomen. Forewings opaque, thickened, reticulate, mottled same as body, variably marked with blackish that often forms an irregular, transverse stripe across center. Additional concentrations of blackish mottling are variably present at the base of the forewings with jagged striations of black near apices. Costal area opaque, same coloration as discoidal area with base predominantly tinted dark gray. Male hindwings entirely hyaline, primary veins occasionally interspersed with darker pigmentation, smaller venules whitish to clear. Female hindwings somewhat extended past forewings. Discoidal and anal areas deep brownish to black with hyaline venation; apices opaque, mottled.

Abdomen. Male abdomen somewhat broadened with tergites II-VI and sternites II-VI each bearing small dorso- and ventrolateral lobes, respectively. Female abdomen broad, tergites II-VI bearing foliaceous dorsolateral lobes with obtusely angled margins. Sternites III-VI bear circular to oblong-shaped foliaceous ventrolateral lobes with variably ruffled, emarginated margins. Lateral abdominal lobes of female well exposed when wings in repose. Male abdomen colored reddish-brown with scattering of fine, darker mottling. Pigmentation of female abdomen heavily mottled with gray, green and black with blackish median band extending length of body segment on dorsal surface, ventral surface reddish-brown. Supra-anal plate small, triangular. Cerci resemble thick thread, measuring longer than subgenital plate.

Etymology. The specific epithet “quisqueyana” is derived from Quisqueya, a Taíno name for Hispaniola meaning “mother of all lands,” with the Latin suffix -ana indicating association, honoring the species’ endemicity to the island’s mesic and montane zones.

Diagnosis. Male and female. Prosternum pigmented light yellow with large, black maculation between forecoxae. Lateral cervical sclerites pigmented black, thinly margined on anterior with dirty yellow. Forecoxae with 3-4 widely spaced teeth along anteroventral margin. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored orange in male, surface smooth, coxal lobes unicolorous, trochanters pigmented orange, occasionally margined in black around coxal lobes and base of forefemora. Anterior surface of forecoxae colored reddish-brown in female, surface smooth, coxal lobes unicolorous. Foretibiae glabrous. Meso/metathoracic legs glabrous. Male pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation 2.6; pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona 3.5; metazona length to prozona length 1.1; pronotum width at supracoxal dilation to pronotum width at base of metazona 1.4. Female pronotum length to pronotum width at supracoxal dilation 2.5; pronotum length to pronotum width at base of metazona 3.5; metazona length to prozona length 1.2; pronotum width at supracoxal dilation to pronotum width at base of metazona 1.4.

Type Locality. Arroyo Frio, La Vega, Dominican Republic

Distribution. Hispaniola

Measurements. *Male.* Body length 39-47; pronotum length 9.5-12; forewing length 32.5-40; prothoracic coxa length 7.5-8; prothoracic femur length 9-11.5; metathoracic femur length 10.5-12. *Female.* Body length 41-47; pronotum length 11-13.5; forewing length 21-25; prothoracic coxa length 7.5-8.5; prothoracic femur length 12-14; metathoracic femur length 11.5-12.

TAXONOMY

Taxonomic Summary. *Gonatista* currently comprises six described species.

Gonatista Saussure, 1869¹

Gonatista bifasciata (de Haan, 1842) **stat. res.**²

Mantis bifasciata de Haan, 1842

= *Gonatista cubensis* Saussure, 1869³

Gonatista borinquensis **nom. nov.**⁴

Gonatista jaiba Lombardo & Perez-Gelabert, 2004⁵

Gonatista major Caudell, 1912⁶

Gonatista phryganoides (Audinet-Serville, 1839)⁷

Gonatista quisqueyana n. sp.⁸

Tarachodes reticulata (Thunberg, 1815)⁹
= *Mantis reticulata* Thunberg, 1815

Mantis grisea Fabricius, 1793 **nomen dubium**

DISCUSSION

¹ *Gonatista* was introduced by Saussure in 1869 without a formal description. Instead of providing a detailed diagnosis of this new genus, Saussure merely included the genus name within an indented dichotomous key from his *Essai d'un Système des Mantides*. While this placement offered a general sense of the distinguishing features used to separate *Gonatista* from related genera, it lacked a comprehensive description typically expected when erecting a new genus. Saussure subsequently flushed out the description of this genus in his works between 1870-1872.

It should be noted that Saussure employed a deliberate cross-referencing strategy between his 1871 *Mémoires pour Servir à l'Histoire Naturelle du Mexique* and his *Études sur les Insectes Orthoptères* within the *Mission Scientifique au*

Mexique, which was issued incrementally between 1870 and 1874. Both works cite each other, with the 1871 volume of *Mémoires* referencing the 1872 publication date of the Mantidae fascicles of *Études* and vice versa. This reciprocal citation pattern strongly suggests that at least parts of the *Étude* fascicles were available to Saussure by 1871 and that he strategically referenced forthcoming or contemporaneous fascicles to establish continuity and authority across his publications. This tactic further supports the conclusion that the *Études sur les Insectes Orthoptères* was released over several years, beginning in 1870, rather than being published all at once at a later date. Saussure's cross-referencing serves as evidence that parts of both works were already in circulation and being used for taxonomic decisions before their final compilation and wider distribution.

Female holotype of *Mantis bifasciata*. Naturalis Biodiversity Center. Photo authored by Charlotte Hartong.

² Fabricius (1793: 22) described *Mantis grisea* from a male specimen that he had examined from the British Museum in London. The original description of this species is as follows:

M. thorace laevi, elytris alisque griseo hyalinis fusco maculatis.

Habitat — — *Mus. Britann.*

Media. Antennae desunt. Caput & thorax grisea, immaculata. Elytra grisea, hyalina maculis plurimis, fuscis, sparsis. Alae itidem griseo hyalinae nervis fusco punctatis. Pedes antici femoribus margine superiori subdilatae, inferiori spinoso. Pedes reliqui griseo fuscoque varii.

The Latin text translates to English as follows:

Mantis with a smooth thorax, and elytra and wings grayish hyaline, spotted with dark.

Habitat — — British Museum.

Medium size. Antennae are missing. Head and thorax are gray, unmarked. Elytra gray, hyaline with numerous, scattered, dark spots. Wings likewise grayish hyaline with dark spotted veins. Forelegs with femurs slightly dilated on the upper margin, spiny on the lower. The other legs are varied in gray and dark.

The holotype of *Mantis grisea* is lost and no illustrations of the specimen exist; all that we have that defines this species is Fabricius' Latin description of the museum specimen. However, there are several key points that contribute to an argument against Fabricius' original description of *grisea* being representative of *Gonatista*. Specifically, Fabricius described the thorax of *grisea* as smooth, whereas *Gonatista* species exhibit a pronotum with salient tubercles, giving it a distinctly lumpy appearance. Additionally, the unmarked thorax of Fabricius' holotype diverges from the contrastingly colored and darkly maculated prosternum found in the population referred to as "*grisea*". Furthermore, the simple spotted patterning of the *grisea* forewings does not align with the more complex and mottled forewings that are characteristic of *Gonatista*. Thus, although the original description of *grisea* may be open to interpretation to some degree, the primary elements suggest that *grisea* is not a

member of *Gonatista* but more probably representative of the Indian genus *Humbertiella*.

Given that *Gonatista* is precinctive to the Caribbean and North America, an accurately listed type locality for *grisea* would be most helpful toward clarifying the true identity of this species. However, unlike the other fifty species of Mantodea, Phasmodea and Mantispids that he described within *Entomologia Systematica*, Fabricius denoted the habitat of *grisea* with the notation "— —". This notation is most peculiar, as Fabricius routinely suggested type localities for the Mantodea species that he described, even if these locations were completely erroneous or little more than educated guesses based upon the poor record keeping of the collector or the cabinet owner.

Fabricius visited London on at least seven different occasions between 1767 and 1787 to examine the insect specimens from the private collections of his high society contacts in addition to those specimens that were deposited within the British Museum. Prior to the 1793 publication of *Entomologia Systematica*, Fabricius described only two Mantodea specimens from the British Museum, *cancellata* and *urbana*, both in 1775. This suggests that the *grisea* holotype was not present among the museum's Mantodea material until after 1775 and that Fabricius most likely examined this specimen during his last visit to London in 1787. Although the *grisea* holotype may have been acquired by the British Museum through purchase or exchange from various global regions, it most likely originated from a British Empire colony, where natural history specimens were commonly and conveniently sent back to London for study. Between 1775 and 1787, the British Empire's colonial involvement in North America and the Caribbean was marked by significant political and military upheaval, most notably the American Revolutionary War and its aftermath. Although Britain still controlled several Caribbean islands during this time period, the instability of the region during a catastrophic war for the Empire makes it highly improbable that the *grisea* holotype originated from this area of conflict during this time period. In contrast, between 1775 and 1787, the British Empire's involvement in India was marked by significant expansion and consolidation of power, primarily

through the activities of the British East India Company. This context makes it more plausible that the *grisea* holotype originated from India, a region actively contributing natural history specimens to the British Museum, rather than the conflict-ridden areas of the declining British colonies in North America.

Given the absence of a type specimen and the inconsistencies between Fabricius' original description and the morphological traits of *Gonatista*, *Mantis grisea* is unlikely to belong to this genus. Instead, its characteristics more closely align with *Humbertiella*, an Indian genus, and historical context suggests its holotype likely originated from India rather than the Caribbean or North America. Since the original description lacks sufficient detail to confidently align *grisea* with a known species of *Humbertiella*, it should be designated as *nomen dubium*.

Anderson (2021: 100) successfully argued that Caudell's 1912 synonymization of *bifasciata* and *cubensis* with *reticulata* was unfounded, as it lacked justification, ignored earlier taxonomic work, and was based solely on male specimens while disregarding the female type material of both Cuban species. Given the differences in body size, the geographic range, and the absence of *reticulata* in Cuba, Anderson pointed out that both *bifasciata* and *cubensis* are more accurately treated as junior synonyms of *grisea*, in line with the earlier classification by Saussure & Zehntner (1894: 159). Consequently, *Mantis bifasciata* de Haan, 1842—the earliest available name considered a junior synonym of *grisea*—should be reinstated as a valid species to refer to the species from the Caribbean and North America previously known as *grisea*. The female holotype of *bifasciata* is present within the insect collection at the Naturalist Biodiversity Center in Leiden, therefore a neotype designation is not justified or allowed under the ICZN Code.

³ Saussure (1869: 61) described *cubensis* in his *Essai d'un Système des Mantides*, the same publication in which he established the genus *Gonatista*. As *cubensis* was the only species originally included in *Gonatista*, it is the type species of the genus by monotypy. Saussure did not designate a holotype when describing *cubensis*;

his original description indicates that multiple specimens—both males and females—were examined, thereby constituting a syntype series. Saussure noted that the material originated from Cuba but did not initially specify the institution where the specimens were deposited. Although many of Saussure's types are housed at the Muséum d'Histoire Naturelle in Geneva (MHNG), Roy & Cuche (2008: 9) previously reported that the MHNG held no specimens attributable to the *cubensis* type series, leading to the belief that the syntypes were lost. However, Pfäuti and Hollier (2012: 263) later corrected this record by documenting the existence of *cubensis* type material at the MHNG. They reported that four male and two female syntypes of *cubensis* were located. Of these, two males and one female are labeled "Cuba M. H. de Saussure," and two males and one female are labeled "Cuba (Mr.) Poey." This labeling corroborates Saussure's (1871: 23; 1872: 231) own statement that the *cubensis* type series was collected by himself and Professor F. Poey in Cuba. Thus, the *cubensis* syntype material is extant and deposited at the MHNG, rectifying previous documentation about its loss.

Rather than continuing to recognize these specimens under the name *cubensis* in his subsequent treatments, or assigning them to *bifasciata*—also described from Cuba 27 years earlier—Saussure (1871: 23; 1872: 231) instead attributed the series to *grisea*, a species whose identity was already ambiguous. At this point, Saussure erroneously synonymized all previously published names associated with *Gonatista*, including *phryganoides*, *bifasciata* and *cubensis*, listing them all as junior synonyms of *grisea*. This suggests that Saussure came to believe that his own *cubensis* type series merely represented *grisea* rather than a distinct species. When he initially established *Gonatista* and described *cubensis*, he made no mention of either *grisea* or *bifasciata*, despite their prior descriptions. It appears that by 1871, Saussure had backtracked—retrospectively folding these names, along with *phryganoides*, into *grisea* without due consideration of the divergent type localities, original descriptions, or type material. Moreover, there is no indication that Saussure had access to the *phryganoides* holotype, which would likely have remained in the possession of Count Pierre François Marie

Auguste Dejean at the time and was not available for study. As a result, no direct comparison could be made between this distinctive Hispaniolan species and the Cuban *Gonatista* material that Saussure examined. Similarly, there is no evidence that Saussure ever examined the now-lost *grisea* holotype, reportedly deposited in London but missing since the early 19th century. In the absence of critical comparisons, Saussure erroneously assumed that all of these names referred to the same species—represented by the Cuban material before him—despite significant differences in provenance and morphology.

The concept of *grisea* was further complicated by Westwood (1889: 4), who listed *nigropunctata* Goeze, 1778 as a synonym of this species. *Mantis*

nigropunctata is an epithet that was assigned by Goeze to an unnamed, crude illustration of Seba. This illustration features a specimen (presumably female) with yellow hindwings that are margined in black—a character wholly absent within *Gonatista*. As Anderson (2024a: 60) noted, unlike many of Seba’s other engravings, which are often highly exaggerated, this particular illustration seems to be identifiable to genus and likely represents the first known depiction of *Macrolatens brunneri* (Fruhstorfer ex Kirby, 1904). However, due to a lack of definitive evidence, the name *nigropunctata* cannot be confidently assigned to any known species and should be classified as *nomen dubium*.

Illustration variants of female “*Gonatista grisea*” Saussure, 1872: 231, Plate V, Figure 1

The process of creating and reproducing colored illustrations in 18th and 19th-century naturalist works involved several meticulous and labor-intensive steps, reflecting the era’s technological constraints and the high value placed on detailed scientific illustration. Artists began by making detailed drawings of the subject, often using collection specimens as a reference. These drawings were then engraved by hand onto metal plates, typically copper, which allowed for finer

detail than woodcuts. Once the plate was prepared, it was inked with black and used to print the images onto paper. This process could be repeated many times, making it possible to produce multiple copies of the same image. After printing the outlines of the depicted specimen, the images were often hand-colored by separate artists using watercolors. The hand coloring was done on each individual print, leading to slight pigmentation variations between copies.

Male specimen of “*Gonatista reticulata*” [now *Gonatista borinquensis* holotype] examined and labeled by Caudell. Dorsal habitus (top left), ventral habitus (top right), label (bottom). Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History. Photos authored by Gavin Svenson.

⁴ The species concept of *Mantis reticulata* has remained poorly defined since the epithet was introduced by Thunberg in 1815. Saussure (1871: 23) was first to address the ambiguity surrounding the name, tentatively listing it as a synonym of *grisea*, a position he maintained for two decades. Kirby (1904: 270) later removed the query and formally recognized *reticulata* as a junior synonym of *grisea*. Caudell (1912: 160) examined several *Gonatista* specimens housed at what is now the Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History. He assigned the name *reticulata* to two male specimens collected in Puerto Rico, stating: “For a third species, also from the West Indies, I arbitrarily use the name *reticulata* of Thunberg,” thereby acknowledging that the designation lacked any specific or justified taxonomic basis. This application of *reticulata* by Caudell constitutes a

misidentification, as Thunberg’s original description is vague, lacks a definitive locality, and refers instead to an African species belonging to the genus *Tarachodes* (Anderson, 2024: 12). Accordingly, the name *reticulata* is not available for the Puerto Rican population of *Gonatista*, which Caudell misapplied the name to. To resolve this long-standing taxonomic confusion, a replacement name—*Gonatista borinquensis*—is herein proposed for the Puerto Rican species misidentified as *reticulata* by Caudell (not *reticulata* Thunberg, 1815). The epithet *borinquensis* is derived from “Borinquén,” the indigenous Taíno name for Puerto Rico, and honors the species’ connection to the island. The surviving male specimen that was examined by Caudell and misattributed to *reticulata* is here designated as the holotype of *borinquensis*.

Male holotype of *Gonatista jaiba*. Dorsal habitus (top left), ventral habitus (top right), label (bottom). Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia. Photos authored by Gavin Svenson.

⁵ *Gonatista jaiba* was described by Lombardo and Perez-Gelabert (2004: 38) from a single male specimen collected in Oviedo, Pedernales Province, Dominican Republic. The species was established based on distinct genitalic features that differed notably from all other *Gonatista* species examined. Morphological comparisons with a broad series of “*reticulata*” specimens revealed no significant differences in external metrics, but the genitalia of the holotype exhibited unique sclerite configurations considered diagnostic at the species level. The holotype’s type locality lies within the Jaragua Peninsula xeric zone, an exceptionally arid and ecologically isolated region in the

southwesternmost part of Hispaniola. This area, part of the broader Enriquillo–Bahoruco–Neiba depression, is characterized by saline soils, sparse xerophytic scrub, and extreme lowland dryness—conditions not found elsewhere on the island or in the wider Caribbean. In contrast, other *Gonatista* populations are distributed across the more mesic, seasonally dry, or montane habitats of central and eastern Hispaniola. The biogeographic isolation and unique microclimatic pressures of the Jaragua Peninsula likely contributed to the speciation event that gave rise to *jaiba*. The female of this species remains unknown.

Male holotype of *Gonatista major*. Dorsal habitus (top left), ventral habitus (top right), label (bottom). Smithsonian National Museum of Natural History. Photos authored by Gavin Svenson.

⁶ Caudell (1912: 161) examined two male specimens housed in the U.S. National Museum (now Smithsonian), originating from the Dominican Republic, which he used for his description of *major*. The original description was notably brief and comparative in nature. Caudell remarked only that the general coloration of this species is lighter than the other species that he examined and that it is decidedly larger. He further noted that while the infuscation of the forewings are no more extensive than in “*grisea*”, it is concentrated into distinctly larger blotches—resembling the pattern seen in “*reticulata*”. The male holotype of *major* remains available for

study, as are the specimens to which Caudell referred under the names “*reticulata*” and “*grisea*”, allowing for direct comparison and reevaluation of his taxonomic conclusions. The female of this species remained undescribed until La Greca (1940: 306) formally characterized it, twenty-eight years after Caudell established the species. In addition to its notably larger body size, *major* is distinguished by a uniquely broad and flattened ootheca, contrasting with the smaller, elongate-triangular oothecae of its congeners. Oothecae of *major* also have a uniquely thick, spongy outer wall compared to the thin, hardened outer wall of other *Gonatista* oothecae.

Male specimen of *Gonatista phryganoides*. Dorsal habitus (left), ventral habitus (right). Anderson Collection Las Vegas.

⁷ This species represents the first true member of *Gonatista* to be formally described and remains the most morphologically distinctive species within the genus. Audinet-Serville based his description on a single male specimen that was sourced from the renowned collection of Pierre André Latreille, six years after Latreille's death in 1833. The male holotype is reportedly housed at the Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle (MNHN) in Paris, where Latreille had served as curator and later professor. Audinet-Serville noted that the specimen possessed forewing maculation resembling that of large Trichoptera (caddisflies), inspiring the species' name, while the female of the species remains unknown. Following Latreille's death, his entomological collection was acquired by Count Pierre François Marie Auguste Dejean. Dejean's expansive holdings, including Latreille's material, were ultimately incorporated into the MNHN's collections, where many of Latreille's original specimens are preserved today. In addition to the MNHN, parts of Latreille's collection that were transferred through other collectors now reside in the Oxford University Museum of Natural History,

forming part of the historically significant Latreille-Dejean-Lepeletier holdings within the Hope Entomological Collections.

Caudell (1912: 162) correctly removed *phryganoides* from synonymy with *grisea* and reinstated it as a valid species within *Gonatista*. In his examination of the *Gonatista* material housed at the U.S. National Museum (now Smithsonian), he identified a series of six male specimens collected from the San Francisco Mountains of the Dominican Republic. Caudell attributed these specimens to *phryganoides*, noting their distinctiveness. In addition to being markedly smaller than any other known species in the genus, *phryganoides* is distinguished by its elytral maculation, which consists almost entirely of small dots—lacking the large, elongate splotches characteristic of the larger congeners. Anderson (2021: 118) erroneously reported this species as occurring in Puerto Rico. To date, no definitive evidence confirms its presence outside of Hispaniola. The female of this species remains unknown.

Male holotype of *Gonatista quisqueyana*. Dorsal habitus (left), ventral habitus (right). Anderson Collection Las Vegas.

Female allotype of *Gonatista quisqueyana*. Dorsal habitus (left), ventral habitus (right). Anderson Collection Las Vegas.

⁸ In his 2021 Caribbean treatment of *Gonatista*, Anderson (2021: 120) united the Puerto Rican population, now referred to as *borinquensis*, with the Hispaniolan population, now identified as *quisqueyana*, treating both as conspecific under the historically misapplied name *reticulata*. This decision was based on prevailing interpretations that regarded *reticulata* as a widespread Caribbean species occurring across both islands. Subsequent to that publication, Anderson (2024) undertook a comprehensive reexamination of Mantodea material originally described by Thunberg. This investigation revealed that *reticulata* was historically misapplied to *Gonatista*, as the type specimen was determined to represent an African species belonging to *Tarachodes*. This finding invalidated the application of *reticulata* to the Caribbean taxa and necessitated a nomenclatural correction. Given this revelation, the composite concept of “*reticulata*” as applied to both Puerto Rican and Hispaniolan material was re-evaluated. Quantitative morphological differences, combined with clear biogeographical separation—two distinct islands divided by a 155-mile marine barrier—demonstrate that the two populations represent reproductively isolated species. Although males of *quisqueyana* and *borinquensis* are superficially similar in appearance, females of the two taxa exhibit far more pronounced differences.

This pattern, wherein female morphology offers greater taxonomic resolution than male characters, is well-documented across multiple Neotropical Mantodea genera. The current species concept of *quisqueyana* supports the hypothesis that the Hispaniolan and Puerto Rican populations represent distinct evolutionary lineages arising from adaptive radiation rather than recent inter-island dispersal of a single species. This interpretation is further supported by the fact that representatives from both island populations have been documented for well over a century, suggesting long-term independent trajectories.

The female allotype of *quisqueyana* was encountered and collected in a dense ravine area within the private garden of Maribel Armenteros in the Dominican Republic, a site that has yielded multiple Mantodea specimens over the past decade. The specimen was first observed by entomologist Dr. Justin Runyon (University of Montana), who was on site conducting research on Diptera alongside Sardis Medrano. The female was flushed from the trunk of a tree during sweep netting and collected following coordinated effort. Additional male specimens, included as paratypes, were attracted to terrace lighting at the same locality.

Male holotype of *Mantis reticulata* [now *Tarachodes reticulata*]. Dorsal habitus (left), ventral habitus (right). Museum of Evolution, Uppsala University. Photo courtesy of Hans Mejlon, Curator of Entomology.

⁹ Thunberg (1815: 288) noted that the origin of *Mantis reticulata* was “Insula Barthelemi” or Saint Barthélemy, a small volcanic island of the Lesser Antilles located 150 miles east of Puerto Rico. The collection label, written in Thunberg’s own hand and still associated with the *reticulata* holotype, reads “Barthel. Fahlberg.” Here, “Barthel.” clearly refers to Saint Barthélemy. “Fahlberg” is believed to be the surname of the individual who either collected the specimen or from whose collection Thunberg acquired it. The species name *reticulata* has been confused for well over a century and incorrectly associated with *Gonatista*. The photograph of the holotype reveals that *reticulata* is actually a member of *Tarachodes*, making it the first species of this genus ever described. One of

the more obvious discrepancies supporting this reclassification is the orientation of the head capsule. The *reticulata* holotype exhibits an opisthognathous head orientation, where the head is directed backward, with the mouthparts pointing backward and downward—a characteristic feature of *Tarachodes*. In contrast, species belonging to *Gonatista* have prognathous head capsule orientations, where the head is directed forward, with the mouthparts pointing forward or slightly downward. No specimens of *reticulata* have been recorded from Saint Barthélemy aside from this isolated report by Thunberg. Given that *Tarachodes* is precinctive to Africa, it is evident that this type location is erroneous, a common issue with many Mantodea records from this era.

LIVE SPECIMEN OBSERVATIONS

01, *Gonatista bifasciata* adult male. Lake Jackson, Brazoria County, Texas, United States 07.27.2017 (Photo: Monica Krancevic)

02, *Gonatista bifasciata* adult male. Valdosta, Lowndes County, Georgia, United States 10.15.2021 (Photo: Michael Broam)

03, *Gonatista bifasciata* adult female. Lehigh Acres, Lee County, Florida, United States 01.10.2015 (Photo: Kara Tyler-Julian)

04, *Gonatista bifasciata* adult female deimatic display. Lehigh Acres, Lee County, Florida, United States 12.12.2015 (Photo: Kara Tyler-Julian)

05, *Gonatista bifasciata* male nymph. Tiger Creek Preserve, Polk County, Florida, United States 08.18.2023 (Photo: Clint Gibson)

06, *Gonatista bifasciata* female nymph. Fruit Cove, Saint Johns County, Florida, United States 07.25.2023 (Photo: Tori Francis)

07, *Gonatista bifasciata* ootheca. Homosassa, Citrus County, Florida, United States 12.30.2018 (Photo: Masumi Palhof)

08, *Gonatista borinquensis* adult male. Utuado, Utuado, Puerto Rico 01.15.2025 (Photo: Sara Puentes)

09, *Gonatista borinquensis* adult male. Rio Abajo, Puerto Rico 10.03.2015 (Photo: Ricardo Valentin-de la Rosa)

10, *Gonatista borinquensis* adult female. Barina, Yauco, Puerto Rico 08.03.2021 (Photo: Alexander Murray)

11, *Gonatista borinquensis* adult female. Maricao, Puerto Rico 07.02.2013 (Photo: Alfredo D. Colon Archilla)

12, *Gonatista borinquensis* female nymph. Puerto Rico 05.25.2015 (Photo: Alfredo D. Colon Archilla)

13, *Gonatista borinquensis* female nymph. Maricao, Puerto Rico 08.23.2017 (Photo: Alfredo D. Colon Archilla)

14, *Gonatista major* adult male. Barreras, Azua, Dominican Republic 08.18.2022 (Photo: Julien Touroult)

15, *Gonatista major* adult female. Jamao al Norte, Espaillat, Dominican Republic 11.26.2022 (Photo: Harvey Luis Garcia Bencosme)

16, *Gonatista major* adult female. Altamira, Puerto Plata, Dominican Republic 06.21.2020 (Photo: Lisa Johnson)

17, *Gonatista major* female nymph. Ebano Verde Scientific Reserve, La Vega, Dominican Republic 07.10.2014 (Photo: Eladio Fernandez)

18, *Gonatista major* ootheca. Altamira, Puerto Plata, Dominican Republic 08.08.2020 (Photo: Lisa Johnson)

19, *Gonatista phryganoides* adult male. Jarabacoa, La Vega, Dominican Republic 10.29.2020 (Photo: Carlos de Soto Molinari)

20, *Gonatista quisqueyana* adult male. Arroyo Frio, La Vega, Dominican Republic 09.28.2022 (Photo: Maribel Armenteros)

21, *Gonatista quisqueyana* adult male. Arroyo Frio, La Vega, Dominican Republic 08.20.2024 (Photo: Maribel Armenteros)

22, *Gonatista quisqueyana* female allotype. Arroyo Frio, La Vega, Dominican Republic 12.21.2019 (Photo: Maribel Armenteros)

23, *Gonatista quisqueyana* adult female. Arroyo Frio, La Vega, Dominican Republic 12.24.2019 (Photo: Carlos de Soto Molinari)

24, *Gonatista quisqueyana* male nymph. Arroyo Frio, La Vega, Dominican Republic 08.20.2022 (Photo: Carlos de Soto Molinari)

25, *Gonatista quisqueyana* ootheca. Arroyo Frio, La Vega, Dominican Republic 12.21.2019 (Photo: Maribel Armenteros)

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